

Deliverable 2.1

Action Plan for the Large-scale awareness and public engagement events

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Action Plan for the Large-scale awareness and public engagement events

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1. Executive Summary

The Transition2bio project builds upon the most relevant communication and education EU-funded projects and initiatives to contribute to the implementation of the updated 2018 EU Bioeconomy Strategy and promote the transition towards more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyles by implementing an integrated package of activities addressing a wide range of target stakeholders.

In the frame of the Work Package 2 (WP2), Transition2bio will promote the transition towards more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyles by informing and providing education through a wide range of awareness-raising and public engagement activities:

- Large-scale events in 6 EU countries
- Seven ‘Hands-on labs for kids’ activities
- At least four info-educational games targeting kids and teenagers
- Three ‘Training of teachers’ activities to exploit the educators’ multiplier effect in reaching young generations
- Two school competitions involving kids and teenagers
- Social media awareness and communication activities on four platforms (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube)

The following sections provide action plans to implement the above-mentioned activities, building upon the assets developed in previous projects (e.g., BIOVOICES, Biobridges and LIFT projects). **Section 3** is focused on providing a guide to organize large-scale events (task 2.1). **Section 4** dives into the topic of hands-on-labs for kids (sub-task 2.2.1), providing an action plan and examples for organizing the labs in different formats and contexts. In **section 5**, an overview of several info-educational games (sub-task 2.2.2) that can be used and combined with other Transition2bio events, that developed within the frames of Transition2bio and other projects, is provided. The concept and guidelines for organizing Training for teachers (sub-task 2.2.3) is described in **section 6**. The action plan for organizing school competitions is included in the **section 7**. The last section **8 presents** a strategy for animation of the social media to increase the impact and effectiveness of the Transition2bio awareness and public engagement activities.

2. Introduction

Transition2BIO is a 24-month Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project that aims to promote the transition to a **more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyle by means of the bioeconomy**, contributing to the implementation of the updated 2018 European Bioeconomy Strategy. The project will build upon the results of the most relevant communication and education EU-funded projects and initiatives and implement an integrated package of **communication, awareness-raising and educational activities**, while actively **engaging the wider public, Member States and Regions** on the one hand, and expanding the **European Bioeconomy Network**¹ and furthering its activities.

More specifically, the **strategic objectives** of the Transition2BIO project are defined as follow:

- Valorise and exploit sectoral communication tools and activities developed at national, regional and local levels by EU-funded bioeconomy projects and other relevant initiatives.
- Raise awareness on the bioeconomy and its related environmental and socio-economic impact on European citizens through a range of communication activities.
- Contribute to the transition to a more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyle through engagement and educational activities;
- Contribute to the deployment of the regional bioeconomy strategies by providing Member States and Regions with methodologies, mentoring, capacity building, tools and materials to raise awareness of and communicate the bioeconomy.
- Facilitate the identification of the educational and training needs in view of creating an innovative ecosystem for the bioeconomy.
- Strengthen the European Bioeconomy Network to maximise the collaboration among EU-funded bioeconomy projects and their collective impact.

Those strategic objectives are to be implemented through the **main activities** of the project which will focus on:

- Collecting available awareness-raising, communication and educational material deriving from relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives to be put at the wider public's disposal through the creation of an online library. The material will also be organised in the form of toolkits tailored to the needs of the stakeholders identified and targeted by the project, namely:
 - the DEMAND side (i.e., the general public with particular attention being paid to children and teenagers, students and young researchers, public procurers interested

¹ The [European Bioeconomy Network](#) (EuBioNet) is a proactive alliance of EU-funded projects promoting, communicating and supporting the bioeconomy through knowledge sharing, networking, mutual learning, and coordination of joint activities and events.

- in adopting sustainable and/or bio-based solutions at national, regional and local levels, etc.);
- the SUPPLY side (i.e., the primary sector, Bio-based industries, SMEs and large enterprises, etc.); and
 - MULTIPLIERS AND SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT (i.e., Citizens' organisations, NGOs and other associations, brands, retailers, educators, influencers, the media, policy makers, public authorities at national, regional and local levels, networks and clusters, etc.).
- Interacting with the wider public during large-scale awareness raising events, placing great emphasis on children and teenagers through hands-on labs, info-educational games and school competitions, with teacher trainings being a key component.
 - Supporting Member States and Regions in the implementation of awareness and communication activities for the design and deployment of their Bioeconomy Strategies by providing them with mentoring, mutual learning and bioeconomy-related capacity building activities.
 - Identifying future skills needed for the Bioeconomy and the related educational needs.
 - Expanding the European Bioeconomy Network by attracting new relevant partners (e.g., BBI-JU, BIC, the SCAR Bioeconomy Strategic Working Group, the BIOEAST Initiative, etc.) and animating the collaboration among them to consolidate and reinforce the existing synergies, maximise opportunities and the impact of bioeconomy promotional activities.

This deliverable aims to provide partners with a methodology covering the following necessary aspects for the successful organisation of events:

- Strategy to maximise the impact of the events
- Activities to be organised
- Monitoring and impact assessment of organised events compared to predetermined expectations (see the Transition2bio event and activity planning and reporting guide).

Remark: *This deliverable has been prepared at the beginning of the project and constitutes the first version of the "Action Plan for the Large-scale awareness and public engagement events" based on the information provided in the Description of the Action. The deliverable will be updated throughout the project implementation based on the experience of project partners with implementation of the activities. The final and more detailed version of the Action plans will be prepared at the end of the project (in M24 – December 2022).*

3. Action plan for the large-scale events

Within the Transition2bio project, six (6) large scale events² will be organised in 6 EU countries (IT, BE, PT, SK, GR, DE) reaching at least 40.000 participants and each target group defined by the project (DEMAND, SUPPLY and MULTIPLIERS/SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT). These activities will be organised in the context of large events already attracting thousands of participants addressing topics like sustainability, green lifestyles, science and innovation, citizen science, etc.

To ensure that the expected number of large-scale events is organised, and the target groups and desired number of participants are reached, an online future events calendar was developed (see section 3.1.2).

Due to the COVID-19 preventive measures, several events identified in the preparation phase were cancelled or postponed. Therefore, mitigation measures have been proposed by the respective partners. The table below provides an overview of the large-scale events and measures proposed to ensure the objectives are met:

The expected impact of the large-scale events on their participants is:

- Raised awareness of sustainable production, consumption, and lifestyles.
- Ability to make more informed choices when buying and consuming products.

To ensure these impacts, Transition2bio partners will deploy a wide range of awareness and public engagement activities by organising large-scale events within the context of existing international fairs, conferences, exhibitions, etc. The organisation will benefit from the ongoing collaboration with the organisers of some of these events – e.g., Innova Camera (organiser of Maker Faire Rome, European version) and Frascati Scienza (organiser of the European Researchers’ Night in Italy).

The preparation of a large-scale event can be complex and takes place over several months before the event. It’s helpful to break the work down into tasks distributed over a longer period:

M0	M2	M4	M5	M6	M7 - EVENT	M8 ->
Define the purpose and unique selling point						
Define the target group and available resources						
Make a list of relevant events						
	Define the objectives, duration and space available					
	Make a preliminary list of the activities					
	Select the event					
	Contact the organiser and register					
		Adjust the activities				
			Prepare and produce materials and equipment			
			Design evaluation			
			Promotion			
				Set the scene		
				Implement		
				Collect feedback		
					Evaluate	
					Make recommendations	

² In general, large-scale events can be described as complex events attended by a large number of visitors, taking place over multiple days and/or locations – e.g., conferences, fairs, exhibitions and professional seminars.

The following sections will guide you through the preparation, implementation and evaluation phases of a large-scale event.

For more information about monitoring and impact assessment of organised events compared to predetermined expectations please see the Transition2bio event and activity planning and reporting guide).

3.1 BEFORE the event

3.1.1 Define your unique selling point

Before you start planning a large-scale event, you need to define your 'unique selling point', or what makes your project and its activities different from what other projects can offer to the organiser of a large-scale event.

The unique selling point can be defined by addressing the following (Reid, 2011):

1. List the features and benefits that are unique about the Transition2bio project results.
2. Decide what requirements of the organiser are being specifically met by the project.
3. Create short, clear, and concise phrases highlighting the project activities.
4. Answer the organiser and attendees' question: 'What's in it for me?'

1. Features and benefits that are unique about the Transition2bio project results

Think about the unique assets of the Transition2bio project:

- What contents and tools can be brought to the event?
- What target groups can you attract?
- How do you plan to engage visitors?

Transition2bio has analysed and summarised the needs and interests of the target groups, as well as the most successful designs of actions and activities to create awareness, communication and education toolkits.

Understanding of the target groups' needs in terms of:

- What to communicate (contents)
- How to communicate (channels, messages, and tools)

Best practices

- The organisation of the events in Transition2bio is based on the successful formats of the 'Bioeconomy Village' and the 'BioART Gallery' implemented in BIOWAYS, Biobridges and BIOVOICES, showcasing bio-based products in everyday situations and allowing visitors to touch and feel what the bio-based economy is. The most successful practices and content in awareness-raising and public engagement activities for the bioeconomy have been identified and enriched by new outputs developed within the Transition2bio project.

Experience / Expertise / Network

- Thanks to an optimal combination of knowledge and content, Transition2bio partners can develop concepts to explain, demonstrate and help participants experience the

bioeconomy and its benefits in various contexts. Please see section 3.1.5 for examples of large-scale event designs.

- In addition to that, the consortium partners have established collaborations with wide networks of stakeholders at the national and transnational level.

2. What requirements of the organizer are being specifically met by your project

Look at the website and the main topics of the event you would like to participate in. Think about how Transition2bio fits into the event and what requirements are met. In the application form, you might be asked to answer questions such as:

- How does your project fit within the event?
- How does your project fit within the EU development priorities?
- What are the current impact and the sustainability potential of your project?
- Does your project bridge across several themes or sectors or build on other projects?

4. Create short, clear, and concise phrases about your project activities.

To create these phrases, think about the objectives of the event matching with the project objectives:

- What will the visitors learn?
- What should the visitors remember?
- In what way should their attitudes be changed?

5. Answering the organizer and attendees' question: "What's in it for me?"

What added value or additional benefits can you bring to the event? Are you able to involve a great speaker, experts, scientists or a well-known influencer, or organise a workshop?

Usually, participation in a large-scale event requires paying a registration fee. However, if your concept provides added value for the organisers of the large-scale event, better conditions can be negotiated.

3.1.2 Identify the target group

Each stakeholder category (DEMAND side, SUPPLY side, MULTIPLIERS and SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT) is reached by at least one large-scale event, addressing the largest number of bioeconomy domains.

To ensure that each of the target groups is reached, an online 'future events calendar' was developed and is regularly updated.

Table 1: Future events calendar – Large-scale events

City	Title of the event	Start date	End date	Target group (DEMAND, SUPPLY, MULTIPLIERS)	Status	Related WP	Scope (local, national, international)	Partner responsible (organizer)
Rome	Maker Faire Rome	October		ALL	TBC	WP2	European	FVA
Nitra	Agrokomplex 2021 Alternatively 2022	19.8.2021	22.8.2021	ALL	TBC, situation is improving - highly probable we will be able to organize it. Application submitted in May, cooperation with the Slovak Bioeconomy Cluster discussed.	WP2	National	PEDAL
Nitra	Agrofilm	October		ALL	the organizers will be contacted in June 2021	WP2	National	PEDAL
TBD	Consumers International Summit 2021/ 2022	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBC	WP2	European	LOBA
Frascati	European Researchers Night 2022	September 2021	September 2021	ALL	TBC	WP2	National	FVA
Brussels	Science is wonderful	TBD	TBD	ALL	TBC. FVA and APRE sent the T2BIO proposal to the EC in Feb 2020	WP2		APRE, FVA
Lisbon	Planetiers World Gathering 2022	April; October	April; October	ALL		WP2	European	LOBA
Berlin	Shaping the Bioeconomy' Exhibition	June 2021	July 2021	DEMAND	Still TBC if it can take place (if not, it will certainly be postponed). The situation in Berlin changes on a weekly basis with regards to the	WP2	Regional	BIOCOM

					organisation of exhibitions.			
Berlin	Bioeconomy Camp 2021	30.09.21	01.10.21	DEMAND, MULTIPLIERS	TBC	WP2	Regional	BIOCOM
Munich	Munich Science Days	08.10.21	10.10.21	DEMAND, MULTIPLIERS	TBC	WP2	Regional	BIOCOM
TBD	Sustainability Week 2022 (7th annual meeting - The Economist)	TBD	TBD	ALL	TBC	WP2	European	APRE
TBD	EU week of Regions and City 2022	TBD	TBD	Policymakers, researchers, demands, multipliers	TBC	WP2	European	APRE
online	Bioeconomy Day 2021	27/5/2021	27/5/2021	Students, teachers, citizens	FINISHED	WP2	National	APRE
Trento (Trentino Alto-Adige)	IFIB - International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy	30/9/2021	1/10/2021	ALL	In progress (working with Cluster SPRING)	WP2	European	APRE
TBD	EU Green week 2022	TBD	TBD	ALL	Date TBC	WP2	European	APRE, FVA
Thessaloniki	Researchers Night	1/9/2021	1/9/2021	ALL	TBC	WP2	European	QPLAN
Mazzara del Vallo (Sicily)	Blue sea land	27/10/2021	31/10/2021	ALL	TBC	WP2	European	FVA

There are a few considerations to be taken into account when selecting an event in the context of which a large-scale event can be organized by Transition2bio:

- Does the selected event fit in with the objectives of the Transition2bio project?
- What are the concept and scope of the event?
- Is the target group of the event in line with the target group of the project?
- What do you want to achieve? What is the expected impact?
- Is it the timing right?
- Are the budget and timescale realistic?
- Who needs to be involved in the event (internal staff, external experts, other partners)?

- How will the event be evaluated?

3.1.3 Main objectives of the large-scale event

The expected outcomes of the large-scale events defined by the Transition2bio project are:

- To deploy a wide range of awareness-raising and public engagement activities targeting the DEMAND, SUPPLY and MULTIPLIERS/ SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT.
- To increase the target stakeholders' knowledge and awareness of the potential benefits of all the bioeconomy sectors.

The expected impact of the Transition2bio large-scale events is to contribute in raising awareness of sustainable production, consumption and lifestyles and encourage people to make more informed choices when buying and consuming products.

When planning a large-scale event, it is recommended to formulate objectives and key messages (main take-aways) for each event, reflecting the national or regional context and the specific needs of the event visitors. A few tips to define the objectives, key messages and contents are provided below:

- Keep it simple
 - What is the main objective of the large-scale event in one sentence?
 - What are the specific objectives of the event? Create up to 4 key messages around the main objective.
- Language
 - Use lay language, avoid jargon and technical language.
- Keep messages
 - Concise, relevant, compelling, memorable and real.
 - Based on a solid scientific background.
 - Tailored to the target audience.
 - Few and briefly presented, showing the benefits of visiting the stand (e.g., 4 questions about a topic to be answered in the event).
- Contents
 - Use stories and storytelling, showing positive examples.
 - Combine data and information with values, emotions and personal experiences.

Thinking about the objectives will help you in the following steps:

- Selection and adjustment of the activities
- Promotion of the event
- Complying with GDPR
- Evaluation of the event
- Documentation of the impact

3.1.4 Sort out the budget

Drawing up a budget is crucial in the early stages of event planning. It not only helps to identify other aspects of your plan that need to be considered, but it also helps to avoid unpleasant surprises (unexpected costs, etc.).

According to the grant agreement, the amount of 3000 EUR is allocated to the budget of each Transition2bio partner responsible for organizing a large-scale event.

The main item costs can be broken down into 4 major categories:

- Registration fee and related costs
- Staff, speakers and external experts (internal staff, scientists, facilitators, etc.)
- Materials, equipment and related services (production, purchase, transport, insurance, etc.)
- Marketing and promotion (social media campaign, etc.)

The costs of items will change. Remember that you will need to revisit the budget and ensure that it reflects any changes or updates.

3.1.5 Set-up of the large-scale events

The large-scale events in Transition2bio can be seen as big 'educational parties'. To ensure the events are successful, it is essential to create the right atmosphere for inspiring and learning.

The limitations of space, available budget, involvement of other projects or duration of the event will be the key factors in designing the scope and agenda of the event.

It is not necessary to have the agenda finalised before you start promoting the event. However, it is recommended to have the concept confirmed as early as possible, as the information is important for communications and/or negotiations with the organisers.

1. Invite the visitor with your design

- Design is the most basic and effective way to bring traffic to your exhibition booth. Certainly, not just any design can encourage the attendees to have a brief visit. The booth must not be simply attractive but also meaningful in all its forms. Choose what fits your budget whether it's custom-built or modular and make the best use of the stand with a design that is in line with the project visibility guidelines.
- Transition2bio builds on the assets of the BioART Gallery consisting of various visual materials and samples of bio-based products that can be selected according to the available space.

2. Develop bold and clear communication:

- Use strong graphics and large signage; be creative by using the floor of your stand design.
- Do not focus on conveying information only, think about how to attract attention.
- Host a live webcast for those who are unable to attend the exhibition.

3. Ensure fun-filled interaction:
 - Host a Game: Gamification is a very popular trend used at exhibitions. Introducing a game for visitors to play will help you attract more people, engage in meaningful conversations and create memories.
 - Online educational games
 - Online / offline quizzes
 - 'Escape room'
4. Organize workshops and discussions:
 - Visitors are looking for new, innovative and workable solutions to existing challenges. Develop topics that will provide answers or offer solutions to some of their challenges.
 - Offer a 'meet the scientist' experience
5. Think about social engagement:
 - Encourage group interaction and discussion. Most visitors come in groups, and visiting is very often a social experience.
 - Visitors read little of the text on display; objects may open up many different learning conversations that relate to people's own experiences:
 - Start from what the visitors already know
 - Tips for an activity encouraging group interactions and discussions:
 - Dynamic Diptychs
Suggested time: 5–20 minutes
Resources needed: A partner and a camera
This playful activity encourages visitors to make connections between images related to a biobased material and product. The idea is to collaborate and create a series of diptychs – combinations of materials and biobased products
6. Provide your new connections or visitors of your booth with a chance to sit and take a break:

The space within your booth may be small, but it can be still used effectively.

 - Have a Coffee Point: create a sitting area inside where the attendees can sit together with the T2bio partners, create connections with researchers, makers, etc. or relax.
 - Give freebies: A simple yet effective trick is to distribute free promotional items to visitors. Whether it's a branded pen or a snack or drink, attendees will surely stop by to have a look. This will eventually give you a chance to start a conversation.
 - Educational videos can be a great way of capturing and maintaining attention as well as raising awareness.
7. Allow your audience to share stories and memorable experiences from their visits.
 - Create simple props demonstrating what the visitor has learnt that can be used by the visitors when taking pictures at your stand. There can be various props offered, some of them having a start of a sentence, e.g., 'I know ...' on them, which can be combined with a number of answers based on the main takeaway messages to be remembered by the visitors of your stand, e.g., 'what biodegradable means' or 'that plastics can be made from', etc. Please keep in mind that in order to ensure

compliance with the GDPR regulation, no such pictures can be taken and used by the Transition2bio partner. Instead, it is highly recommended to ask visitors to tag @biovoices on social media post or stories, so that we can reshare.

8. Connect with fellow exhibitors:

- Projects focusing on topics related to the T2bio and similar objectives might be participating in the event. Try to get in touch with them in advance to learn if you can join forces in the communication and promotion efforts. This form of communication will also build strong interaction as some of the attendees will be informed about the T2bio stand and might be curious to know more about the project.

9. Involve team members with effective communication:

- Your employees must be well aware of each product and its quality. Above all, they must have high communication abilities to make the visitors feel connected to the topic.

10. Get your smartphone out:

- Visitors are more likely to leave their contact details, complete a survey or view a demonstration on a tablet or a screen than on a long paper form.

One challenging audience to plan for is multi-generational families. There are various approaches to ensuring that even younger visitors are engaged in your content:

- Create a specific place in the exhibition where the family can work together to solve a scientific problem, put a puzzle together or construct something.
- Write a series of child-friendly labels, clearly identified, that address items of interest to the target group.
- Create a separate printed family guide that is given to adults in a group and helps them make the content accessible to younger ages or provides complementary content for younger ages.
- Schedule family programmes throughout the run of the exhibition.

3.1.5.1 Design 1 – Physical event / large space

Design is suitable for exhibition contexts similar to art galleries or exhibitions where large space is provided. It combines the formats of the 'Bioeconomy village' and the 'BioART Gallery' implemented in BIOWAYS, Biobridges and BIOVOICES, existing assets (e.g., the collection of pictures, the BIOVOICES Book for Kids What's bioeconomy?) developed by previous projects, and activities developed by the Transition2bio project. Drawing its inspiration from the BIOVOICES Book for Kids, the design is based on the creation of a specific environment that is well-known to the visitors of specific regions. The design uses existing assets to allow visitors to learn about bio-based alternatives in an interactive way.

- Materials to be used:
 - Visual materials (BioART Gallery maxi-pictures and boards)
 - Samples of bio-based products
 - Experiments and workshops

- Online Games
- Format:
 - Combine the exhibition and interactive activities inspired by an escape room:
 - Create a selection of maxi pictures (boards, roll-ups, posters) and samples of bio-based products to create an environment the visitors are familiar with, e.g., countryside, seaside.
 - Children are more excited by things that are familiar, or that they have prior knowledge of. The role of the adult is important in guiding children through exhibits, answering and posing questions. Therefore, it's important that adults feel like they have the resources made available to them to answer those questions, or to help them know what they are doing.
 - Create separated areas, each of them dedicated to a bio-based material or product that can be found or used in the selected type of environment
 - Prepare a set of questions related to the topic of each of the areas, supporting dialogue amongst visitors
 - Combine visual materials, a selection of samples and simple experiments (see section 4)
 - Provide an award (e.g., the BIOVOICES Book for Kids What's bioeconomy?)
 - Create an area where the visitors can relax and enjoy the pictures
 - Offer coffee, serve it in edible coffee cups and provide a video demonstration of how the coffee grounds will be used
 - Use big screens to attract visitors (to play educational videos or let visitor play educational games)
 - Use the space for organising a lecture/discussion
 - Collect feedback
 - Use the space to engage visitors through casual conversations and asking questions, allow visitors to leave feedback using a wall and sticky notes or an interactive screen.

3.1.5.2 Design 2 - Physical event / inside / small space

Based on design 1, this design is adjusted to a smaller space. The aim is to focus on a small selection of materials and bio-based products to demonstrate the availability of bio-based solutions in everyday life. The use of augmented reality, online educational games and videos is strongly recommended.

- Materials to be used:
 - Visual materials (BioART Gallery roll-ups/posters)
 - Samples of bio-based products
 - Experiments and workshops
 - Online games
 - Feedback
- Format: see Design 1

3.1.5.3 Design 3 - Physical event / outside

Taking into account the pandemic restrictions, Design 3 was developed as an alternative of a large-scale event organised as an open-air event.

Materials to be used include for example roll ups, posters or samples of bio-based products that will not be damaged if displayed in an open-air area and can be packed easily. Electronic devices should be used in sheltered areas (e.g., a tent) only. Visitors can be encouraged to use their own devices (e.g., to play online games, provide feedback, scan QR codes, view augmented reality)

The event can also be combined with Hands-on labs for kids.

3.1.5.4 Design 4 - Online event

Due to the highly unpredictable pandemic situation and restrictive measure that might hinder organizing physical events, a virtual design has been developed.

It is based on the info-educational game Town2bio developed by FVA (see section 5). The aim of the game is to provide a gamified solution to explore the toolkit contents related to various areas of bioeconomy that will be available in T2BIO in virtual environment. The game will also provide an area for virtual events that will be organized by different actors willing to provide workshops around bioeconomy. The platform will allow interactivity between participants using the proximity concept (if they get close, they can interact) with private areas that will allow also networking activities.

Thanks to the above-mentioned features, the info-educational game can be connected to any online large scale event, offering various kinds of experience:

- Inspire and Inform in a webinar lead by an inspiring speaker
- Learn together, exploring what bioeconomy is about by playing the game or in an interactive session, e.g., an interactive workshop or a hands on lab
- Network during virtual coffee breaks.

Format:

- Online environment of the info-educational game Town2bio that is being developed by FVA
- The area for virtual events that can be used to organize interactive sessions. However, organizing such activities can be proposed to the organizer of the whole event and included into the main agenda of the whole event.

3.1.6 Building the ultimate event team

The duration and size of the event, as well as the type of activities selected for your large-scale event will also affect the size and composition of the team that needs to be involved.

In the case of small events, your internal team may personally be handling most of the preparation and implementation of the large-scale event. However, in the case of longer events, it takes an organized team to ensure smooth implementation or expertise.

Tips:

In the case of small teams, people are wearing multiple hats. Think of their strengths and weaknesses when assigning roles (e.g., communication with visitors, communication with partners, coordination of schedules, etc.).

If your event includes educational elements, you'll need to identify experts for the sessions. When contacting an external expert, provide a brief description of the event and audience, and also the potential benefits or added value that can be appealing to the experts. Decide in advance if you can cover some costs related to the participation of external experts.

3.1.7 Promotion of the event and involvement of visitors

Promoting the large-scale event is another important step to ensure its successful organization. While the promotional activities will be carried out in collaboration with FVA, the task leader of Task 2.3., a few recommendations are provided below.

When preparing the promotion activities, think about the added value for the visitors (objectives). Why should they visit your booth? What "AHA MOMENT" would you like to create?

Based on the objectives of the large-scale event, start thinking about how to promote the event:

- Create key messages
 - define one key message per target group (DEMAND, SUPPLY, MULTIPLIERS) you want to convey
 - what are the main takeaway messages to be delivered?
- Select communication channels
 - Provide sufficient information to the organizer of the event
 - Use the project and your organization communication channels:
 - website
 - social media
 - newsletter
 - email marketing
 - Use your organization network to spread the word about the event via partners' communication channels
- Check available resources to promote the event
- Create a set of communication channels according to the target group and be consistent:
 - use the same graphic layout
 - keep the same messages communicated
- Select one thing to communicate:
 - one simple fact, useful tip, etc.
 - remember, use messages about the event that are clear, and concise
 - use a simple language
- Use simple pictures illustrating the message
- Use what is already available

- materials developed in the project – e.g., present one idea or fact from the BIOVOICES Book for Kids “What's bioeconomy”? and use a picture from the book
- Start well in advance and post regularly
 - create an event on Facebook
 - create a plan of contributions to be posted and shared via different channels
- Involve influencers
- If the event is taking place throughout several days, do not forget to post on your social media regularly.

3.1.8 Time plan

Putting together a comprehensive checklist of all the activities, tasks and roles needed will help you to determine the number of people required to ensure the smooth implementation of the large-scale event. Think also about how many people need to be at the event at any one time, for how long, what extra roles might be needed (unpacking and installing things, ensuring breaks, etc.).

Establish a schedule and update the team on completed tasks, pressing issues, concerns, and coordinate next steps.

3.2 DURING the event

3.2.1 Setting the scene

Big events are characterised by a high number of exhibitors. It would be wise to learn about other exhibitors taking part in the event and think about how to attract visitors to your booth.

- Make it look different!
 - Stand out – roll-ups and posters are typical elements
 - Use something different - hanging visual materials, gadgets, screens, nice smell, activities – e.g., experiments (also adults like to make things)
 - Less is more:
 - It is better to have less materials/ information to avoid overwhelming the visitors. Be clear and consistent.
 - Try to be memorable

3.2.2 Engagement of the visitors

Remember there are many exhibitors and activities competing for the attention of the visitors. Think about how to draw their interest and make them want to come to you:

- Place samples and simple posters asking a question about terms people often mix up (e.g., “compostable” or “degradable”, etc.) at various spots of the venue, inviting visitors to your booth
- Consider incorporating onsite technologies like a social media wall
- Actively invite the visitors and make them curious:

- Hostess showing a sample of a biobased material and asking a simple question (e.g., do you know what this is made of?) – at several places of the venue

Do not forget to collect all documentation to report and further promote the event:

- Documentation ensuring compliance with GDPR (Informed consent form and information sheet), where necessary
- Audio-visual materials (pictures, recordings, videos). Please remember to take pictures from behind with no faces in order to avoid breach of the GDPR regulation
- Results of activities (e.g., presentations, products from the experiments)

3.2.3 Collecting feedback

The expected impact, outcome and objectives of the large-scale event should guide you through the process of defining the type of information to be collected and the most appropriate methods to do so.

- Type of information
 - Quantitative information about your event
 - Total number of visitors
 - Number of visitors per category
 - Qualitative information about the event to understand the satisfaction and knowledge gained by the visitors
- Collection methods:
 - Personal interviews conducted during the event
 - Feedback collected using
 - interactive screens
 - a wall with questions and post-it notes to provide feedback
 - Online tools, e.g., Mentimeter

Besides collecting feedback from participants, remember to collect feedback also from the team members and external collaborators participating in the event. To motivate stand visitors to fill out the feedback questionnaire or participate in quizzes / competitions offer them a gadget from the project.

3.3 AFTER the event

3.3.1 Evaluation of the event

Now it's time to debrief your event. Capture the feedback collected and all follow-up notes that will help you organize future events following the same type of program.

Before drawing conclusions and recommendations, summarize the findings, which are validated data without any interpretation, e.g., "x number of attendees out of y total number of visitors said xxx". Even though it might be difficult not to jump to conclusions, it would be just an unfounded assumption.

Having the findings completed, you might ask “so what?”. Conclusions answer this question. They can be described as interpretations or explanations, created by looking at the findings in the bigger picture.

The last question to be answered is “now what? To build on what works or improve what does not in a project, what would be recommended to do? Recommendations need to be specific and actionable.

3.3.2 Reporting

Reporting of an event includes financial and technical reporting.

In technical reporting you should demonstrate that the event contributed to achieving the expected impact. Use the information from the feedback collected to show:

- Activities carried out, objectives accomplished, feedback received
 - Process the qualitative information, e.g. the level of satisfaction, new knowledge obtained, etc.
- Contribution to achieving the KPI-related targets
 - Number of participants
 - Target groups engaged
- Lessons learned
 - Summarize the main recommendations and lessons learned to improve the organization of events in the future.
 - The D2.1, which has been created as a living document, will be further improved, and updated throughout the project.

4. Action plan for the Hands-on labs for kids

4.1 BEFORE the event

4.1.1 Aim of the Hands-on labs for kids

The aim of this task is to implement at least seven "Hands-on Labs for Kids" activities in Italy (IT), Austria (AT), Portugal (PT), Slovakia (SK), Greece (GR) and Germany (DE) reaching at least 300 kids.

Kids play an important role in driving the change toward a more sustainable consumption and lifestyle, not only because they are the tomorrow's adults, but also because they act as multipliers inside the families (especially with older generations, like grandparents).

The goal of such experiential labs for kids is to raise awareness and facilitate the understanding of bioeconomy through hands-on activities, informing and educating kids about bioeconomy areas (e.g. natural ecosystems, primary production, processing), for the production of food, materials and energy, by touching, feeling, smelling, and exploring the bioeconomy.

In order to help guide young people in making sustainable choices in their formative years, the labs for kids seek to communicate knowledge of the bioeconomy and bio-based solutions in an easy and comprehensive way. This is achieved by focusing on familiar and everyday environments that kids find themselves in.

4.1.2 Explore options to link the T2bio activities to existing events and networks

The goal is to deploy these activities in contexts where the kids and families are already participating (museums, festivals, fairs, school activities, etc.), thus maximising the impact. In addition, they will be tied into other tasks, specifically Task 2.1 Large-scale awareness and public engagement events and Sub-task 2.2.3 Training for teachers.

The labs for kids build on experiences like the "Bioeconomy Village" and the "BioART Gallery" implemented in BIOWAYS and BIOVOICES at large-scale international exhibitions. They also draw from the BIOVOICES book for kids and the accompanied extensive knowledge and testing that went into creating the book for children. All the information in the book was validated by 32 experts from academia and industry in a scientific committee.

4.1.3 Topic of the Hands-on labs for kids

Given the broad range of environments and cultures in which these labs will be implemented, it is essential that a certain degree of flexibility remains in choosing the topics for the lab experiments. With this in mind, however a general set of core topics have been identified based on familiar environments for children: the home, school, countryside, seaside, and the city (supermarket and park). Based on these contexts, kids will make small experiments that will touch on a number of important aspects of the bioeconomy, including the circular economy, sustainable production, consumption and lifestyle, climate change, ecosystems, biodiversity and planet's protection, end-of-life, biodegradability/composability, biorefinery, biomass, etc.

4.1.4 Scope of the Hands-on labs for kids

The Hands-on labs for kids (Design format 1, 2, and 3) will be deployed as a small booth(s) in different environments and countries. In order to organise the logistics and promotion of the hands-on labs, the Transition2BIO partner (the host partner) present in the country will seek support from the Sub-task 2.2.1 leader, BIOCUM AG. BIOCUM will provide support for the preparation of the hands-on labs (e.g. conceptual support, briefing documents, experiment leaflets). The host partner is responsible for practical implementation and ensuring the presence of a researcher, professor, teacher or scientist able to explain the experiments to the kids and their accompanying relatives and answer questions in the local language. The experiments will be shown by researchers, animators or project partners, previously prepared, in order to provide the necessary instructions to repeat the experiments at home with the parents.

4.1.5 Expected outputs and outcomes

Expected outcomes include outreach and involvement of at least 300 kids in experiments aimed at demonstrating with bio-based products and explaining the bioeconomy from Italy (IT), Austria (AT), Portugal (PT), Slovakia (SK), Greece (GR) and Germany (DE).

Expected outputs include methodologies for the organisation of awareness-raising activities targeting kids and specific guidelines on how to create experiments for kids at home. In addition, DIY videos will be created where physical events cannot take place due to COVID-19 restrictions.

4.1.6 Identify the target group

The labs for kids are targeted at children aged 5 to 8 years old. However, the lab experience will also help to educate kids parents, grandparents, teachers and other adults that participate together with the children in their experiments.

4.1.7 Time plan

In view of the COVID-19 pandemic that continues affecting social gatherings across Europe in 2021, Design format 1 will concentrate most of the hands-on labs for kids in 2022 and deliver them in physical settings to the extent possible. Below is a tentative list of events that could be targeted in the six countries where the hands-on labs for kids are meant to take place:

Table 2: Future events calendar - Hands on labs for kids

Country	City	Title of the event	Start date	End date	Target group (DEMAND, SUPPLY, MULTIPLIERS)	Status	Related WP	Scope (local, national, international)	Partner responsible (organizer)
Italy	Frascati	European Researchers Night	September 2021	September 2021	ALL	TBC	WP2	National	FVA
Germany	Berlin	Bioökonomie.de Exhibition	November		DEMAND, MULTIPLIERS	November at the Naturkunde Museum. A small event with around 50 people max	WP2	National	BIOCOM
Germany	Berlin	International Green Week	January		DEMAND, SUPPLY, MULTIPLIERS	Exact date TBC	WP2	European	BIOCOM
Italy	Rome	Maker Faire	October		ALL	TBC	WP2	European	FVA
Italy	Rimini	ECOMONDO	October		SUPPLY, MULTIPLIERS	TBC	WP2	European	UNIBO
Slovakia	Nitra	Agrofilm	04/10/21	7/10/2021	ALL	the organizers will be contacted in June 2021	WP2	European	PEDAL
Slovakia	Nitra	Agrokomplex	19.8.2021	22.8.2021	ALL	TBC, situation is improving - highly probable we will be able to organize it. Application submitted in May, cooperation with the Slovak Bioeconomy Cluster discussed.	WP2	European	PEDAL

Slovakia	Zvolen	National forestry days	August		DEMAND	the organizers have been contacted and are interested in T2bio. it is not clear if the event will take place	WP2	Regional	PEDAL
Austria	TBD	Lange Nacht der Forschung	2022		DEMAND, MULTIPLIERS	TBC	WP2	National	ZSI
Austria	Vienna	Maker Fair Vienna	2022		DEMAND, SUPPLY, MULTIPLIERS	TBC	WP2	National	ZSI
Austria	Salzburg	Kinderstadt	July 2022		DEMAND, MULTIPLIERS	TBC	WP2	Regional	ZSI
Portugal	Lisbon	Planetiers World Gathering	April; October		DEMAND	TBC	WP2	European	LOBA
Portugal	TBD	Consumers International Summit	2022		DEMAND	TBC	WP2	European	LOBA
Greece	Halkidiki	Blue Halkidiki	3/7/2021	9/7/2021	DEMAND	Imminent	WP2	Regional	QPLAN
Italy	Lazio region	Startupper School Academy	1/10/2020	1/6/2021		In progress	WP2	Regional	FVA
Italy	Roma	Traing course for high school students - Ostia (Roma)	4/6/2021	4/6/2021	Demand	Finished	WP2	Regional	FVA

4.1.8 Budget

The total budget for each lab is 1.000 EUR (of 7.000 EUR total). Each host partner is responsible for tracking their allotted budget expenditures.

4.1.9 Set-up of the Hands-on labs for kids

4.1.9.1 Design 1 - Large-Scale Physical Event – multiple mini labs

Drawing on previous successful experiences like the “Bioeconomy Village” and the BioART Gallery implemented in BIOWAYS and BIOVOICES at large-scale international exhibitions such as Maker Faire and Researchers’ Night etc., a number of small mini kids’ labs can be organized throughout the event. As opposed to having 1 Hands-on Lab in one set location, it is possible to reach different target audiences with less effort. In order to combine resources and increase impact, multiple mini labs will be organized throughout large physical events/fairs.

It is essential to work closely with local partners and enlist researchers (anywhere from 50 to 60, depending on the size of the event) who can help perform the experiments with kids. While researchers often already have a number of experiments that can be adapted to children, a set of standard and easy to implement experiments help compliment these activities and help

ensure a broad range of activities across different areas of the bioeconomy are touched upon. These activities can be easily adapted depending on the resources existent in the region.

Hands-on Experiments (based largely on the *BIOVOICES Book for kids “What’s bioeconomy?”*)

- Setting 1: **Overview** of the bioeconomy

Experiment type	Blind Box Sensory activity
Materials	Feel: straw, fungi, orange peel, coffee, eggshells, wood chips with corresponding bioproduct of your choice Taste/Smell: apple, orange, fungi, olives, algae, tomato, coffee with corresponding bioproduct of your choice
Instructions	Feel different feedstocks and learn about their related bioeconomy applications in everyday life and try to match the feed stock with the bioproduct. (see <i>Figure 1</i>) Smelling/tasting Sensory Bottles and try to match with bioproduct.
Learning	Learn about the different feedstocks and their potential as products.

Experiment type	Traditional versus bio-based products
Materials	Cut out of pictures or real products if available.
Instructions	Using the BLOOM resource pack ANNEX 1 a box of materials or pictures will be created and children will need to divide them into two groups of bio and non-bio / fossil fuel products (see <i>Figure 2</i>). The teacher gives each group a box with several items or pictures (e.g., usual plastic bottles and recycled or bio-based products; non-bio-based fuels and bio-based fuels resulting from bioeconomy; electronic pieces; cotton material and polyester material. If the teacher can find real products, that will be preferable.
Learning	Learn about the differences between bio and non-bio-based products

- Setting 2: Bioeconomy in the **Home**

Experiment type	Coffee Scrub
Materials	Coffee grounds, oil (jojoba, olive or coconut).
Instructions	Mix 2 tbsp. of used coffee grounds with 1 tbsp. of oil (jojoba, olive or coconut). Use as a gentle scrub for body and face
Learning	Learn about the many uses of waste products . Coffee grounds can also be used for: Bioplastics, Microgranules for cosmetics, Textiles, Paper, Coloring pigments, gardening.

Experiment type	Biodegradable pots
Materials	Eggshells, water, cornstarch, white vinegar, stove/heating plate, microwave/oven
Instructions	Mix in a pan 2 tbsp. of crushed eggshells with 2 tbsp. of water, 3 tbsp. of cornstarch and half of a tbsp. of white vinegar then mix for a few minutes. Put the pan on the stove and mix contents until it thickens. Mold the mixture around the inside of a paper cup. Bake it in microwave (500 watt) for 3 min. or in the oven (180°C/356 °F) for 15 min.
Learning	Learn about the production of biomaterials from organic waste.

- Setting 3: Bioeconomy at **School**

Experiment type	Natural color fun
Materials	Purple cabbage, water, vinegar, baking soda
Instructions	Dye your t-shirt or paint with flowers or vegetables. For the purple cabbage experiment: Wash half a purple cabbage in a pot of cold water. Divide the used water into 3 glasses. Add 1 tbsp. of vinegar to first glass, nothing to the second and 1 tbsp. of baking soda to the third.
Learning	Learn about natural dyes: What happened? A chemical process changed the colour of the water Learn about the production of clothing : did you know that before modern colors were invented, all clothes were dyed naturally?

- Setting 4: Bioeconomy in the **Countryside**

Experiment type	Seed balls
Materials	Compost, flour, water, seeds
Instructions	Mix 8 tbsp. of compost, 4 tbsp. of flour, 4 tbsp. of water, 2 tbsp. of seeds (grass or wildflowers). Shape the mixture into little balls. Let them dry for at least 24 hours. (see Figure 3).
Learning	Throw them to spread flowers and learn about natural ecosystems .

- Setting 5: Bioeconomy in the **Seaside**

Experiment type	Make a Wind Catcher
Materials	Sticks, string (or seaweed, sea nets), objects from nature (e.g., shells, bits of wood, pebbles)
Instructions	Choose two sticks and an assortment of objects from nature. Cut various lengths of twine or string. Tie the two sticks together to form an X. Tie the nature objects to the sticks. Hang on a tree.
Learning	Observe the objects as the wind catches them. Learn about wind as a renewable energy source. Explain that seaweed is also used to produce bioplastic.

- Setting 6: Bioeconomy in the **City**

Experiment type	Biogas factory in a bottle
Materials	Water, sugar, brewer's yeast, balloon
Instructions	Fill half a glass bottle with water. Add 2 tbsp. of sugar, 1 tbsp. of brewer's yeast, cover with your hand and shake it! Stretch a balloon over the neck of the bottle and after few minutes the balloon will inflate.
Learning	Learn about the power of biogas : Why did your balloon blow up? It was filled up with biogas (see Figure 4).

4.1.9.2 Design 2 - Museum or Summer Camp – 1 lab

In the summer months and in an open air setting a kids lab can be set up in connection with summer school/camps or museum activities. In this scenario, the previously listed experiments will be set up in one area as opposed to being spread out throughout a large-scale event.

Experiment type	Blossom plantable paper from paper scraps
Materials	Used paper, seeds
Instructions	Video tutorial
Learning	Plantable paper is made for primary school children, who start to ask questions about the world around them and contributes to paper recycling. It could contain seeds of fruits, vegetables and flowers.

4.1.9.3 Design 3 - In School Activities – 1 lab

As long as kids are still in school, hands on labs for kids can be combined with Subtask T2.2.3 Training for teachers. T2.2.3 will organize at least 3 workshops in form of face2face trainings or webinars in Italy (IT), Austria (AT), and Greece (GR). At the end of a training, a kids lab can be set up where the teachers can implement the above listed experiments and directly put to use the knowledge acquired during the teacher training.

In addition to the experiments listed above, for children 8 and above, a more complicated experiment can be organized that makes plastic from potatoes. (see [ALLThings.Bio](#) tutorial and [video](#)).

4.1.9.4 Design 4 - Activities in the home

Activities in the home

If children are unable to be reached at large-scale events, in schools, or summer camps/museums, a number of fun activities can be promoted through online experiences. By combing actions with Sub-task T2.2.2 Info-educational games, a gamified version of the BIOVOICES Book for Kids What's bioeconomy will be created and accessible to all kids from home.

In addition, a number of small videos of DIY experiments will be produced. These will include the above listed simple experiments as well as more complex ones, which require a kitchen or stove. Examples include:

Experiment type	DIY bioplastics from orange peels and ground coffee
Materials	Orange peels to cook (25 g. of orange peel), water for boiling (15ml water), pot, blender, 50 g. corn starch, 2 g. sodium bicarbonate, 5 ml lemon juice, 5 ml sage oil, 5 ml vinegar, stove/heating plate, mold to form a shape, oven 25 g. coffee grounds, 50 g. corn starch, 15ml water, 5 ml vinegar, 5 ml lemon juice, 2 g. sodium bicarbonate, 5 ml sage oil, stove/heating plate, mold to form a shape, oven
Instructions	See Video tutorial .
Learning	Children learn how bioplastics can be made in their own kitchens

Experiment type	Bio-based Disinfectant
Materials	White vinegar, citrus peels, strainer, filter funnel, cup, airtight glass containers.
Instructions	Peel citrus fruit and chop fruit peels. Then collect the peels in a jar. Add white vinegar to jar. Close jar tightly and date. Strain the jar after two weeks and it is ready to use. You can also make vinegar or tea from fruit peels. See video tutorial here or BLOOM resource here .
Learning	Learn about the production of bioproducts from organic waste.

Experiment type	Turning Milk into Plastic
Materials	Milk (1 cup), White vinegar (4 teaspoons), Measuring cup, Measuring spoons, Mug, Paper towels, Spoon, Stovetop oven and pan or microwave, Optional: Thermos, Cookie cutters, glitter, food coloring, markers.
Instructions	More information here .
Learning	Learn about the production of bioproducts from organic waste.

4.1.10 Promotion of the Hands-on labs for kids

4.1.10.1 Promotional materials

BIOCOM AG and the host partner will coordinate with Task 2.3 Leader FVA, to organise prior to each hands-on lab social media awareness and public engagement activities in order to create content connected to the Hands-on Labs for Kids. Given the limited budget for the hands-on labs, the preferred approach to ensure proper promotion prior to the hands-on labs will always be for the host partner to liaise with the third-party involved in hosting the hands-on lab (e.g. larger event organiser, school, summer camp organiser, museum/science hub owner, etc) and with the Transition2BIO partner leading on an activity (e.g. sub-tasks 2.2.3 & 2.2.4) or event (e.g. task 2.1) to scope any budget possibilities or advertisement opportunities. Printed promotional items (e.g., experiment leaflets) that will be displayed during the event will be created by LOBA and translations provided by the host partner.

4.1.10.2 Promotional channels

Regarding the online promotional materials, different social networks will be utilised (*Instagram, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn*) and combined where possible with the promotion of the BIOVOICES book for kids (e.g., social media posts). As many projects' online communication and dissemination tools as possible will be mobilised to promote the hands-on labs (e.g., press release, newsletter, etc).

As regards the offline promotional materials, these will be advertised locally as much as possible, in coordination with the local host or other actors that could help at grassroots level, if possible (e.g., media agency, municipality, etc). These possibilities to open up promotional channels at local level will be examined, well ahead of the hands-on labs, together with the Transition2BIO host partners.

For both types of promotional materials (offline or online), the networks of any third-party involved in hosting the hands-on labs will also be used to ensure an efficient local outreach.

4.2 DURING the event

4.2.1 Setting the scene

In Design format 1 and 2, booth(s) will be set up with attractive and fun signage. In addition, Factsheets (see examples from [Bioeconomy Village](#) and [BIOSTEP](#)) with glossary definitions from the BIOVOICES book for kids will provide clarifying information about the products and resources.

4.2.2 Involvement of the target groups

In Design format 1, the host partner with any needed assistance from BIOCOM will reach out to schools and other members of their networks to ensure their involvement in the physical events.

4.2.3 Collecting feedback

Where possible short quizzes will be provided at the booth(s) to test kids understanding. (see figure 5). These must be provided in the local language.

4.3 AFTER the event

4.3.1 Evaluation of the Hands-on labs for kids

No data will be collected on minors taking part in any of the lab experiments and only photos taken from behind and without faces will be used. The information addressed to the children will be in age-appropriate and plain language that they can easily understand.

However, feedback can be collected by observing how engaged the children were in the experiments and whether the information addressed to them was in age-appropriate and plain language that could be easily understood.

4.3.2 Drawing conclusions and recommendations

Not only will observations be recorded and analysed in a report on the physical events, in collaboration with Subtask 2.2.3 Training for teachers, but teachers will also be questioned on the appropriateness, practicality, understandability, and level of fun and engagement of the activities for kids.

Figure 1: Hands on labs – example of the activity carried out at home

Figure 2: The BLOOM School Box Future Classroom Scenario Building a new environmental future

Figure 3: BIOVOICES Book for Kids "What's bioeconomy?"

Figure 4: BIOChallenge Quiz

5. Action plan for the Info-educational games

As described in the DOA under Sub-Task 2.2.2, Transition2BIO will deliver a set of info-educational games, produced during previous projects where some of the partners were involved (BIOWAYS and BIOVOICES), as well as two additional new games designed and developed to meet the specific needs identified through the activities with stakeholders, in particular teachers and families.

A key strategy in the design of these games was to initiate collaboration with other EU-funded projects in the bioeconomy area, providing additional content for the games based on their research results.

5.1 Available games

Bio...What?

<http://www.fvaweb.eu/biowhat>

Aim: Designed to promote awareness of everyday use of bio-based products.

Description: The game, inspired by Super Mario game, takes the player on a fun-packed adventure on which he/she will encounter all sorts of enemies and traps (the fossil-based products).

The player will discover how some raw materials, from bamboo to elephant poo, can be used to make the products used every day, in a sustainable way.

The game is:

- Available in 6 languages (new languages easy to add)
- Playable in all devices (Desktop PC, Laptops, Tablet, Smart phones)

Deployment: The game has been deployed for single player (available on-line and on the game areas on the exhibition booth during events) and for group session moderated by a facilitator to engage discussions about bioeconomy.

Target audiences: Children and teenagers.

Collaboration: Contents provided by BioSTEP project; concept, design and implementation by BIOWAYS project.

Game piloting:

Individual sessions (668 players)

- Researchers' night in Italy (Frascati, Bologna and Cesena)

- Researchers' night in Portugal (Aveiro)
- Social media promotion and players sharing on Facebook
- Maker Faire (Rome, Italy)

Group sessions (around 300 players)

- 2 sessions at Researchers' night in Italy (Frascati)
- 1 pilot in Italy (Università di Bologna)
- 1 pilot in Chatham UK during THRIVE's Erasmus+ project conference
- 2 school pilots with children in UK
- Maker Faire (Rome, Italy)

Figure 5: Screen shots of "Bio...What?" deployed for single players and for group sessions

BIO Challenge

<http://www.fvaweb.eu/biochallenge>

Aim: Designed to address the main misunderstanding and confusion about bio-economy.

Description: Is a quiz game that poses several questions about bioeconomy, to highlight the clear differences in terminology, between concepts such as “bio-based, biodegradable, compostable, sustainable, organic products”. Each question has a timer to make the game more challenging.

The game is:

- Available in 5 languages
- Playable in all devices (Desktop PC, Laptops, Tablet, Smart phones)

Deployment: The game has been deployed for single players (available on-line and on the game areas on the exhibition booth during events) and for group sessions moderated by a facilitator to engage discussions about bioeconomy and terminology.

Target audiences: Teenagers and Adults

Collaboration: Contents provided by STARProBio project; concept, design and implementation by BIOWAYS project.

Game piloting:

Individual sessions (665 players)

- Social media promotion and players sharing on facebook
- Maker Faire (Rome, Italy)

Group sessions (around 250 players)

- 1 pilot during STARProBio general Assembly (Rome, Italy)
- 1 training seminar (Cesena, Italy)
- Maker Faire sessions (Rome, Italy)

Figure 6: Screen shots of "Bio Challenge" deployed for single players and for group sessions

BioWhaatAR

Aim: This Is an Augmented Reality app game designed to promote awareness about the everyday use of bio-based products.

Target audiences: Children and teenagers

Collaboration: Contents provided by the **BioSTEP** project; concept, design by **BIOWAYS**; technical implementation by the **First Parallel** project (financed under the H2020 programme "a fast track to Innovation").

Deployment: The game has been deployed for single players

Game piloting: Maker Faire (Rome, Italy) (200 players)

How much do you know about bioeconomy?

Aim: Designed to make teenagers compete in a challenging quiz base game.

Description: Is a quiz game that poses several questions about bioeconomy. Each question has a timer to make the game more challenging and at the end of any question the results of the

score of the participants is shown. The faster the players answer the higher score they get. The game was developed using the MENTIMETER platform.

The game is:

- Available in English and French
- Playable in all devices (Desktop PC, Laptops, Tablet, Smart phones)

Deployment: The game has been deployed for group sessions moderated by a facilitator to engage the participants.

Target audiences: Teenagers and Adults

Game piloting:

- Science is wonderful 25-26 September 2019

Figure 7: Screen shots of “How much do you know about bioeconomy?” deployed for group sessions

5.2 DURING the event

Two new games will be designed and developed to meet the specific needs identified through the activities with stakeholders, in particular teachers and families.

5.2.1 What’s bioeconomy – the Book for Kids “What’s bioeconomy?” online

The first info-educational game, is already in the production process and is based on the book for kids produced for the BIOVOICES project.

There will be also available an area for virtual events that will be organized by different actors willing to provide workshops around bioeconomy.

The platform will allow interactivity between participants using the proximity concept (if they get close, they can interact) with private areas that will allow also networking activities.

FVA is exploring different platforms to be used for the implementation of this game.

6. Action plan for the Training of teachers

6.1 BEFORE the event

6.1.1 Aim of the Training of teachers

The main objectives of the Transition2bio teacher trainings are to implement and advance educational opportunities in the bioeconomy, to introduce new skills to allow bioeconomy teaching and learning, to upscale the standards of bioeconomy teaching in Europe as well as to raise the awareness of the bioeconomy in general.

Consequently, following **sub - objectives of Transition2bio teacher training is to:**

(i) Foster awareness and a better understanding of the bioeconomy:

It is important to have a basic knowledge of the bioeconomy, its effects and importance in relation to nature and resources. A sound knowledge base of the bioeconomy helps the teacher a lot in implementing bioeconomy into his day2day teaching in a scientifically correct way.

(ii) Building Confidence:

The transition2bio teacher training also aims to build confidence in the potential of teachers. A trained teacher can essentially face the class with confidence if he/she can build on a sound knowledge of the bioeconomy. The aim is to have educated teachers that can tackle the various questions of the students and foster bioeconomy in the students' mindset.

(iii) Innovative methodologies of teaching bioeconomy:

Through training, the teacher becomes further familiar with innovative methodologies to teach bioeconomy. This might include methods that go beyond a traditional way. In addition, practical experiments or - even better - hands-on experiments should be demonstrated in the training for easy copying in schools.

6.1.2 Explore options to link the T2bio activities to existing events and networks

The teacher training can be related to several other components of T2.2, namely:

(i) Hand-on activities

The development of small-scale hands-on activities can become an extremely valuable resource for the teacher training since teachers will face the same conditions of low budget, limited time resources or simple instructions.

Especially for novice bioeconomy teachers this easy step into some practical experiments is highly attractive. It is advisable to include hands-on activities in a teaching/learning session for students since it also contributes to a high motivation of students. Thus, training the teachers not only to talk about the importance of bioeconomy, but really to demonstrate on effects, handling, etc. is vital.

(ii) Competition for children

Secondly, every school activity can be followed by a call for contributions to the competition. If hands-on activities, teacher training and competition are well aligned, we will at the same time, boost the number of contributions to the competition.

(iii) Other materials

Obviously, there might be other useful sources that can support the facilitation of the teacher trainings like educational games. Depending on the launch of the different tools and materials, the teacher trainings will be adapted in case some materials are of high relevance for teachers and schools.

6.1.3 Topic of the Training of teachers

The topics of the Transition2Bio will be determined by the selection of material in WP1. Only material that is identified by the experts will be prepared for the teacher training. However, certain elements that are requested from a didactical point of view shall be integrated.

Following elements shall be included:

I Welcome and Introduction

- a. Intro and overview about programme and
- b. Timing / timeline
- c. Clarification of:
 - aim of the training
 - rules for participation
 - online training 'etiquette'
- d. Warming up / Motivation:
 - ask for motivation of participation (ie. Pigeonhole)
- e. Expectations
discuss expectations of participants

II Bioeconomy in schools

Introducing Bioeconomy (concepts, tools)

- a. How to create interest ...
- b. Basics on Bioeconomy and implementation to the curriculum
 - importance to make relation to environment of students
 - methods for successful teaching of the bioeconomy
 - hands-on activities for schools

III Concluding

- a. Summarizing results
- b. Evaluation questionnaire (EN, IT)
- c. Concluding remarks and thanks

6.1.4 Scope of the Training of teachers

The trainings will be held in Italy, Greece and Austria with at least 200 teachers. While the Italian and Greek partners will implement it on a national level, the Austrian teacher training will be held in English and will be open for teachers and educators in Europe. Therefore, the training will be held online.

6.1.5 Expected outputs and outcomes

The teacher training is expected to:

- ... raise the tacit knowledge of teachers on bioeconomy in general
- ... foster the understanding and importance/relevance of bioeconomy
- ... gain knowledge on how to raise awareness of students to a responsible handling of natural resources
- ... enrich knowledge on innovative teaching methods to implement bioeconomy in schools including application of hands-on experiments for students
- Gain practical implementation skills (hands-on experiments) for children

Each teacher training will be evaluated towards these expected outcomes (pl. see Annex).

6.1.6 Define the target group

Following target groups have been identified to address:

- Teachers of primary and secondary school level
- Educators
- Employees of museums or exhibitions that address children
- Youth trainers
- Other educators; not specified

6.1.7 Time plan

The teacher training will start with some initial training in Italy already in month 2 of the project (February 2021). The gained experiences will be shared with the partners and will have significant influence on the training to allow adaptation of the concept. Thus, continuous improvement will be made during the lifetime of the project.

6.1.8 Set-up of the Training of teachers

Face-to-face training

6.1.9 Promotion of the Training of teachers

Promotion of the teacher trainings will be made via the national channels of the Italian and Greek partners, but also via related sister projects such as BIOVOICES, BLOOM, PowerfulBIO.

With the support of the dissemination partner as well as the project partners, the teacher trainings will be also promoted via different other channels such as:

- Websites
- Blog entries
- News entries
- Entries in electronic newsletters to div. teacher association (i.e EUN, Ministries of Education, ...)
- Facebook / Twitter / Instagram / LinkedIn

6.2 AFTER the event

6.2.1 Evaluation of the Training of teachers

Each teacher training will be evaluated towards the expected outcomes (pl. see Annex). The trainings will be evaluated via LimeSurvey and is available in English and Italian under:

<https://survey.zsi.at/index.php/794914?lang=en>

6.2.2 Drawing conclusions and recommendations

Insights and recommendations will be done at the end of the teacher trainings and will be included in the reporting. Special attention will be given to major findings that will allow summarizing recommendations for teachers of primary and secondary level.

6.2.3 Reporting

The reports of the teacher training will be included in Deliverable D2.3.

7. Action plan for the School competitions

7.1 BEFORE the event

7.1.1 Aim of the School competition

The main objectives of the school competitions are to:

- raise awareness and foster knowledge of the bioeconomy
- inspire further interest in educational materials on the bioeconomy
- upscale the use of bioeconomy teaching resources
- motivate learning by reward
- reward the most innovative implementations

7.1.2 Explore options to link the T2bio activities to existing events and networks

It is planned to promote the competition at all engagement activities in T2B, particularly in teacher trainings, large-scale events and hand-on labs that take place prior to the competition. At the teacher trainings, participants can be invited to compete with their classes (kids) or to inform teens about the competition (groups can include up to 5 persons). This would ensure that trained teachers use their newly gained knowledge immediately.

7.1.3 Categories of the School competition

The following ideas have been proposed as the categories of school competitions:

- Small videos with mobile phones on production of bioplastic - competitors could invent specific uses preferably to solve specific problems
- Bioplastic → make an art sculpture
- How to make bio-based products from side streams. Ideas on what can be done with the side stream material.
- Short social video to promote bio-based alternatives

Example in Vienna: aquatic plants from the Danube are harvested so that people can swim and use boats (see link). Up till now plants were harvested and composted. BOKU students made trials to produce packaging materials (<https://wien.orf.at/stories/3094159/>).

7.1.4 Expected outputs and outcomes

- New ideas on what to produce with self-made bio-based plastic
- Short videos with students that can be used for further dissemination and awareness raising – could be shown at events, teacher trainings, labs

7.1.5 Identify the target group

- **Competition kids:** younger pupils, school classes as a group, targeting 6-12 - competition addresses teachers with their school classes, one class is one competitor
- **Competition teens:** older pupils: targeting individual pupils or small groups up to 5 between 13-18 (?)

7.1.6 Time plan

This needs to be planned hand in hand with other engagement activities in Transition2BIO such as the teacher trainings. Trained teachers could be important multipliers and competitors, using their newly gained knowledge and experiment with their classes.

A possible time frame for the competition could be: The competition could be open for four months (max 10 months), for example it could be launched in October 2021 and end by the end of January 2022. Winners of each category will be announced by the end of March 2022.

7.1.7 Format

This task is designed to be implemented as an online competition.

7.1.8 Recruiting the Jury members

Organisation of the jury:

- 2 scientific experts
- 2 pedagogical experts
- Open jury: FB

7.1.9 Awards

The following ideas have been proposed as possible awards:

- For the kids: the BIOVOICES Book for Kids “What's bioeconomy” (150 pc are ordered)
- a study trip to a bioeconomy event or a tour to bioeconomy business....
- Bioplastic toolkit with fungus, or a workshop with the bioeconomy companies (ie. Grown <https://www.grown.bio/>)

7.1.10 Set-up of the School competition

The competition will be online and will be disseminated over Europe. An own webpage will be set up in order to allow high visibility and access.

Criteria for participation and selection process will be outlined as well as other necessary information (i.e., review process).

7.1.11 Promotion of the School competition

- A webpage informing about the competition and leading to the submission form should be set up on the Transition2Bio homepage
- To maximize outreach, the competition will run in collaboration with other events i.e. the Transition2BIO teacher trainings, the hands-on activities for kids and the large-scale events.
- Dissemination via other projects and bioeconomy events (ie. STEM Discovery Week)
- Social media (Facebook, Instagram, ...) that are favoured by young people.

7.1.12 Submission

7.1.12.1 Submission period

This will be determined soon. If we follow the timeframe suggested above all information must be submitted by the 31 January 2022 at 23:59 Central European Time (CET) in order to be eligible for the competition. However, there can be adjustments in order to plan the competition in alignment with the teacher trainings. Also, the 2 distinct competitions could have different schedules.

All content included in the submission form (including links with supporting material) must be available to view and download until the end of the submission period (more details will be given in a Terms and Conditions page). Submissions received outside the submission period will not be eligible for participation.

7.1.12.2 Submitted content - first criteria

The submitted content for the competition shall be an original creation.

The submitted work should:

Follow the official submission template provided in the framework of the competition. Consist of one standalone document; no attachments will be considered that are not added to the Annex. Be completely original and not contain any third party's work. By participating in the competition, participants agree to present their submitted content under a Creative Commons License of Attribution ShareAlike CC BY-SA.

7.1.12.3 How to submit (Competition kids and teens)

During the submission period of the competition indicated below, teachers or parents can submit their entries by going through detailed instructions. These instructions will contain a step-by-step guide on how to submit the contribution.

Example

Step 1: Prepare their "..." according to the competition template provided.

Step 2: Fill in the online competition submission form: (lime? survey monkey..., google)

The email address(es) provided in the submission form must be valid...

...

8. Action plan for the Social media awareness and public engagement activities

Transition2BIO will adopt a connected strategy on different social networks (Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube), disseminating content on all channels, allowing to communicate simultaneously with users through a common thread and reach the different project's target stakeholders.

Thanks to the appropriate leverage and involvement of multipliers, influencers and thematic groups, as well as a constant monitoring of the megatrends to identify the correct messages and arguments to be adopted, the social media activity will increase the impact and effectiveness of the Transition2BIO awareness and public engagement activities.

8.1.1 Aim of the social media awareness and public engagement activities

The purposes of the activities that will be carried out on the social media channels cover 3 macro areas:

Communication:

- Raising awareness of the bioeconomy and bio-based products;
- Exploiting communication tools and activities developed by EU-funded bioeconomy projects and other relevant initiatives in the form of Actionable Knowledge for the stakeholders.

Education:

- Identifying educational and training needs;
- Developing engaging and educational activities which will contribute to the transition towards a more sustainable production, consumption and lifestyles;
- Supporting the communication and stakeholder engagement capacities of Member States and Regions.

Support:

- Strengthening the activities of the European Bioeconomy Network, an alliance of more than 70 projects and initiatives promoting the bioeconomy;
- Stimulating the Mobilisation and Mutual Learning of Member States and Regions to boost the deployment of their national and regional bioeconomy strategies.

All the objectives described above will be achieved through various activities (described in the next paragraph), all designed according to the needs of the various target groups identified. For example, the teachers will be offered training courses, educational materials, including games, books for kids and many other tools to raise awareness and educate their students.

8.1.2 Communication channels and target audience

Transition2BIO defined a social media strategy from the start: choosing which channels and when to publish project results, news or information content, being in this way consistent, but tailored to the audience across all communication channels.

The Facebook page reaches different generations and is highly focused on the wider public.

The Instagram page is a key platform for the project to reach the younger generations as well as producers, business representatives, designers and brands.

The Twitter page is a useful tool to communicate with young professionals. Students, teachers, and other stakeholders use it as a pedagogical tool to gain information, interact and engage with each other, participate in their respective communities of interests, and share their insights about specific topics. Furthermore, Twitter is certainly the channel where it is possible to reach the largest number of European projects, organizations and institutional bodies.

The LinkedIn page is the professional social media site where experts share contents, network with other users, and build their personal profile. Via LinkedIn, Transition2BIO will create connections and collaborations with many experts from academia, companies and B2B industries.

Finally, the YouTube page is not only the repository for all the video material developed for communication and dissemination activities, but also one of the leading Internet search engines that allows a huge promotion of the project by allowing the sharing of its contents on all other social channels.

8.1.1 Social media awareness and public engagement activities plan

The social media will implement a daily activity by:

- Constantly publishing information about bio-based products in everyday life and their characteristics.
- Use a gamified approach to collect consumers' perceptions, requirements and ideas (i.e., a weekly quiz asking, for instance to guess the impact of a BB-product compared to a traditional one, or to identify what a product is made from– starch, hemp seeds, etc.)
- Use a series of promo media to engage the participants (mini-videos, animation pools, infographics, questionnaires)
- Publish information about ongoing activities and live events the project is organizing (e.g., in Facebook, asking the people to confirm/check their participation)
- Involving sustainability influences to increase the impact of the Transition2BIO activities.

8.1.2 Expected outputs and outcomes

- Reliable information about bio-based products, delivered in an engaging, but trustable and transparent way
- Good source to get information about ongoing activities, events, news about the bioeconomy
- Innovative formats (games, pools, calls to action, contests, giveaways, DIYs, curiosities, etc.)
- Attractive pictures, videos, infographics

- Storytelling and videos with testimonials
- Active engagement with the audience
- Questions and topics to stimulate the debate and reflection
- Collaborations with multipliers through retweets, hashtags or tags.

8.1.3 Connecting the Social media awareness and public engagement activities with other T2bio activities

The social media channels will be intensively used to promote events and activities before, during and after the events. This activity is meant to be effective in raising the interest and increasing on the one hand the participation and on the another the promotion and communication of the outputs, in the form of insights and Actionable Knowledge.

The social media activities, when connected to events and activities, stimulate the debate on specific topics of discussion and maximise the impact of Transition2BIO.

A very effective practice that will be implemented is the “Live-posting during events” strategy, on Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook, to highlight and disseminate the key points and relevant messages emerging from the discussion.

Live-posting provides engaging, concise content for people who couldn’t attend an event, either in real time or later by searching for the conference hashtag to catch up on the key moments and discussions (by looking at photos, videos, quotes and links and reading key discussion points from throughout the day). On these occasions a specific hashtag will be created to connect all the contents about the event.

Furthermore, all the results stemming out from the project, in form of informative, educational and promotional materials will be shared with a cross-channel strategy.

8.1.4 Monitoring of the Social media awareness and public engagement activities

The monitoring of social media channels will be done monthly, analysing both the growth of followers and the outreach, in terms of impressions, obtained.

Thanks to the engagement activities (quizzes, surveys, etc.), it will be possible to analyse the knowledge, preferences and needs of various groups of stakeholders and tailor the next activities.

8.1.5 Evaluation of the Social media awareness and public engagement activities

On the basis of monitoring, the performance of each channel will be analysed, identifying which strategies and campaigns are most productive and successful.

Furthermore, specific analysis and overview will be made in:

- D2.4 Report on Awareness and engagement of young people - first version.

- D2.5 Report on Awareness and engagement of young people - update.
- D2.6 Report on Social media awareness and public engagement activities - first version.
- D2.7 Report on Social media awareness and public engagement activities – update.

8.1.6 Reporting

The Social media awareness and public engagement activities will be reported in D2.6 and D2.7, while the lessons learnt from these activities will feed T5.4 Lessons learnt and recommendations.

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